

A ROBUST HYBRID CLASSICAL AND QUANTUM MODEL FOR SHORT-TERM WIND SPEED FORECASTING

Andole Pavan Sai¹, Bedike Sudharshan²,

Neelam Vinay Kumar³, Mr. G. Venkataswamy⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,

CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

Power scheduling by power utilities is more difficult than in the past decades because of a high penetration of renewable power generation, such as wind power generation, with highly uncertain and stochastic characteristics. To address this issue, a highly accurate technique for forecasting wind speed must be developed. In this work, a hybrid classical–quantum model is developed to exploit the advantages of two powerful models, a long short-term memory (LSTM) and a quantum neural network. Quantum neural networks, also known as parameterized quantum circuits, act like machine learning models but with greater expressive power. They comprise quantum gates that apply the principles of quantum mechanics in order to achieve quantum advantage. Additionally, to obtain a robust design that is insensitive to seasonal changes in the data, the Taguchi method is used to set up orthogonal experiments to set the hyperparameters of the proposed model. Historical data from seven sites in various countries (Taiwan,

the Philippines, China, and South Korea) are used to forecast 24-hour-ahead wind speeds at the Fuhai wind farm near Taiwan. Comparative simulation results show that the proposed robust hybrid classical-quantum model outperforms current state-of-art models, such as classical nonlinear autoregressive network, random forest, extreme gradient boosting, support vector regression, and classical LSTM.

INTRODUCTION

A.IMPORTANCE OF WIND ENERGY FORECASTING

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, popularly called the ‘17 Sustainable Development Goals’, officially came into force on January 1, 2016. Goal 7.2 concerns the importance of increasing renewable energy in the global energy mix. Over the years, the use of wind energy has grown to supply almost 5% of global electricity [1]. However, owing to its uncontrollable and intermittent nature, integrating wind turbines into energy

systems poses stability and energy management problems. The volatility of wind power generation must be considered to ensure that the spinning reserve of power systems suffices for unit commitment (UC). To take uncertain wind speeds into account, various forecasting methods are continuously being used and improved.

Currently, the five classes of methods are as follows. (i) The persistence method assumes that the wind speed at time 't+1t' equals that at time 't'. (ii) The physical approach [2] uses weather observations and a mathematical computer model of the atmosphere to generate forecasts. (iii) Statistical approaches [3], like autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), estimate statistical relationships among input data. (iv) Artificial intelligence (AI) does not require predefined mathematical models. Examples include random forest (RF) [4], support vector machines [5], support vector regression (SVR) [6], extreme gradient boost (xGBoost) regression [7], nonlinear autoregressive neural networks (NAR) [8], and deep neural networks (DNN). The several types of DNN include autoencoders [9], the deep belief network (DBN) [10], the deep Boltzmann machine [11], the

recurrent neural network (RNN) [12], long short-term memory (LSTM) [13], and the convolutional neural network (CNN) [14]. (v) Hybrid structures combine two or more of the aforementioned and provide favorable outcomes by combining the advantages of two models. Some recent works with outstanding results have involved a combination of CNN and LightGBM [15], and a novel deep convolutional recurrent network to forecast wind power [16].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The biodiversity-wind energy-land use nexus in a global biodiversity hotspot

Wind energy is the leading renewable technology towards achieving climate goals, yet biodiversity trade-offs via land take are emerging. Thus, we are facing the paradox of impacting on biodiversity to combat climate change. We suggest a novel method of spatial planning that enhances windfarm sustainability: investments are prioritized in the most fragmented zones that lie outside the Natura 2000 network of protected areas. We showcase it in Greece, a biodiversity hotspot with a strong climate policy and land conflict between conservation and wind energy schemes. The analysis

indicates that the suggested investment zone supports wind harnessing 1.5 times higher than the 2030 national goal, having only marginally lower (4%) wind speed. It performs well for the conservation of the annexed habitats and species of the two Nature Directives and it greatly overlaps with the Important Bird Areas (93%) and the roadless areas (80%) of Greece. It also greatly overlaps (82%–91%) with the exclusion zones suggested according to three sensitivity maps for bird conservation. Since land use change triggers biodiversity decline, we underline the necessity of such approaches for meeting both climate and biodiversity goals and call for a greater environmental policy convergence towards biodiversity conservation and no net land take.

Probabilistic Short-Term Wind Power Forecasting Using Sparse Bayesian Learning and NWP

Probabilistic short-term wind power forecasting is greatly significant for the operation of wind power scheduling and the reliability of power system. In this paper, an approach based on Sparse Bayesian Learning (SBL) and Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) for probabilistic wind power forecasting in the horizon of 1–24 hours was investigated. In the modeling process, first, the wind speed data from

NWP results was corrected, and then the SBL was used to build a relationship between the combined data and the power generation to produce probabilistic power forecasts. Furthermore, in each model, the application of SBL was improved by using modified-Gaussian kernel function and parameters optimization through Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). To validate the proposed approach, two real-world datasets were used for construction and testing. For deterministic evaluation, the simulation results showed that the proposed model achieves a greater improvement in forecasting accuracy compared with other wind power forecast models. For probabilistic evaluation, the results of indicators also demonstrate that the proposed model has an outstanding performance.

Ensemble Learning for Breast Cancer Lesion Classification: A Pilot Validation Using Correlated Spectroscopic Imaging and Diffusion-Weighted Imaging

The main objective of this work was to evaluate the application of individual and ensemble machine learning models to classify malignant and benign breast masses using features from two-dimensional (2D) correlated spectroscopy

spectra extracted from five-dimensional echo-planar correlated spectroscopic imaging (5D EP-COSI) and diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI). Twenty-four different metabolite and lipid ratios with respect to diagonal fat peaks (1.4 ppm, 5.4 ppm) from 2D spectra, and water and fat peaks (4.7 ppm, 1.4 ppm) from one-dimensional non-water-suppressed (NWS) spectra were used as the features. Additionally, water fraction, fat fraction and water-to-fat ratios from NWS spectra and apparent diffusion coefficients (ADC) from DWI were included. The nine most important features were identified using recursive feature elimination, sequential forward selection and correlation analysis. XGBoost (AUC: 93.0%, Accuracy: 85.7%, F1-score: 88.9%, Precision: 88.2%, Sensitivity: 90.4%, Specificity: 84.6%) and GradientBoost (AUC: 94.3%, Accuracy: 89.3%, F1-score: 90.7%, Precision: 87.9%, Sensitivity: 94.2%, Specificity: 83.4%) were the best-performing models. Conventional biomarkers like choline, myo-Inositol, and glycine were statistically significant predictors. Key features contributing to the classification were ADC, 2D diagonal peaks at 0.9 ppm, 2.1 ppm, 3.5 ppm, and 5.4 ppm, cross peaks between 1.4 and 0.9 ppm, 4.3 and 4.1 ppm, 2.3 and 1.6 ppm, and the triglyceryl-fat cross peak. The

results highlight the contribution of the 2D spectral peaks to the model, and they demonstrate the potential of 5D EP-COSI for early breast cancer detection.

Breast cancer is one of the most prevalent cancers in females and one of the leading causes of cancer death worldwide [1,2]. Early detection and accurate characterization of breast malignancies are crucial factors in breast cancer management and positive treatment outcomes [3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12]. Differentiation of benign from malignant breast lesions can aid clinicians in determining appropriate therapeutic plans. While histopathological examination of breast tissues extracted by biopsy is often required to confirm a suspicious lesion, a mammogram continues to be the gold standard for the detection of breast cancer, but this approach has a high false positive rate [13]. Multi-parametric MRI (mp-MRI), which includes dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI), T₂-weighted MRI and diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) may allow differentiation between benign and malignant breast lesions that present highly overlapping enhancement patterns. However, despite the potential to eliminate unnecessary biopsies and follow-up examinations of benign tumors, mp-

MRI-based breast tumor differentiation still has increased false positive findings.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Killoran et al. [20] used the Strawberry Fields quantum simulator to perform binary classification using QNN. Results show a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve with an area of 0.945, opposed to an ideal value of 1. QNNs have also been applied to other classification tasks like the popular MNIST database, and to regression problems especially in the field of finance. Pistoia et al. [21], used Google's Cirq to simulate PQCs, and demonstrated that it outperformed classical BiLSTM neural networks whenever the noise coefficient was high, and was comparable otherwise.

Noisy quantum computers, with over 100 qubits, have recently been developed and shown to perform tasks better than current supercomputers [22]. While the present is an exciting time to investigate and explore quantum algorithms and other applications, noiseless quantum computers with thousands of qubits are required in order to fully exploit the advantages of major algorithms like Shor's algorithm and Grover's algorithm. Hence, researchers are leaning toward hybrid classical-quantum algorithms as applications of quantum computing to machine learning, with the

general idea of combining quantum and classical computers.

Endo et al. [23] used IBM's superconducting quantum computer to review the results for hybrid quantum-classical algorithms and quantum error mitigation techniques, and determined that future work on error mitigation would be extremely helpful since the use of NISQ devices is limited by large errors

Disadvantages

(1) Physical methods use large mathematical models and require meteorological data on humidity, terrain structure, pressure, and other variables, to obtain accurate results. They are very costly and complicated [2] and are generally not used for short-term forecasting.

(2) Persistence and statistical methods yield accurate results but their accuracies quickly decline as the forecasting horizon increases.

(3) Many machine learning models are used for forecasting and may encounter difficulties when used with data with large standard deviations.

(4) Autoencoders and DBN require large amount of clean data to generate useful results.

(5) Solving the model selection problem for (quantum) deep learning is time-consuming

because the structure parameters and hyperparameters are obtained by trial-and-error thus, the robustness of (quantum) deep learning models cannot be guaranteed.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

(1) A hybrid classical and quantum model is proposed. The LSTM is augmented by a deep QNN, allowing for the seamless fusion of classical and quantum neural networks. This fusion facilitates the transfer of knowledge gained from the classical layers to the quantum layers, empowering the QNN to refine predictions through the principles of the quantum mechanism, resulting in highly accurate 24-hour ahead wind speed forecasts. Consequently, the limitations mentioned earlier (1) and (2) can be effectively overcome.

(2) The hybrid classical and quantum model leverages the complementary learning capabilities of classical and quantum layers. LSTM is known for its proficiency in handling time-series data, while the QNN extends the learning capacity through quantum entanglement. This unique combination enables the network to recognize more complex patterns, which could be challenging for classical models to achieve alone.

(3) Originally, QML was applied mainly to classification problems. This paper aims to

extend its application to regression problems, specifically wind speed forecasting.

Advantages

(i) Quantum parallelism: QNN can process multiple computations simultaneously

through superposition, allowing QNNs to potentially evaluate multiple input states in parallel, making QNNs attractive for certain machine learning tasks. (ii)

Quantum feature mapping: quantum feature mapping allows for efficient encoding of classical data into quantum states, providing a more expressive representation of data. (iii) Quantum entanglement:

Quantum entanglement enables strong correlations among qubits, which can be exploited in QNNs to capture complex relationships between features in the data.

On the other hand, LSTM's ability to capture long-term dependencies, handle sequential data efficiently, and mitigate the vanishing gradient problem makes it a powerful choice for a wide range of sequential data processing tasks in machine learning. Based on these reasons, the proposed model integrates LSTM with QNN.

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Browse and Train & Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Wind Speed Forecasting Status, View Wind Speed Forecasting Detection Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Wind Speed Forecasting Detection Ratio Results, View All Remote Users

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After

registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN, PREDICT WIND SPEED FORECASTING DETECTION TYPE, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

ALGORITHMS

Long Short Term Memory is a kind of recurrent neural network. In RNN output from the last step is fed as input in the current step. LSTM was designed by Hochreiter & Schmidhuber. It tackled the problem of long-term dependencies of RNN in which the RNN cannot predict the word stored in the long term memory but can give more accurate predictions from the recent information. As the gap length increases RNN does not give efficient performance. LSTM can by default retain the information for long period of time. It is used for processing, predicting and classifying on the basis of time series data.

Decision tree classifiers

Decision tree classifiers are used successfully in many diverse areas. Their most important feature is the capability of capturing descriptive

decision making knowledge from the supplied data. Decision tree can be generated from training sets. The procedure for such generation based on the set of objects (S), each belonging to one of the classes C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k is as follows:

Step 1. If all the objects in S belong to the same class, for example C_i , the decision tree for S consists of a leaf labeled with this class

Step 2. Otherwise, let T be some test with possible outcomes O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n . Each object in S has one outcome for T so the test partitions S into subsets S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n where each object in S_i has outcome O_i for T. T becomes the root of the decision tree and for each outcome O_i we build a subsidiary decision tree by invoking the same procedure recursively on the set S_i .

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

- Simple, but a very powerful classification algorithm

- Classifies based on a similarity measure
- Non-parametric
- Lazy learning
- Does not “learn” until the test example is given
- Whenever we have a new data to classify, we find its K-nearest neighbors from the training data

Example

- Training dataset consists of k-closest examples in feature space
- Feature space means, space with categorization variables (non-metric variables)
- Learning based on instances, and thus also works lazily because instance close to the input vector for test or prediction may take time to occur in the training dataset

Logistic regression Classifiers

Logistic regression analysis studies the association between a categorical dependent variable and a set of independent (explanatory) variables.

The name *logistic regression* is used when the dependent variable has only two values, such as 0 and 1 or Yes and No. The name *multinomial logistic regression* is usually reserved for the case when the dependent variable has three or more unique values, such as Married, Single, Divorced, or Widowed. Although the type of data used for the dependent variable is different from that of multiple regression, the practical use of the procedure is similar.

Logistic regression competes with discriminant analysis as a method for analyzing categorical-response variables. Many statisticians feel that logistic regression is more versatile and better suited for modeling most situations than is discriminant analysis. This is because logistic regression does not assume that the independent variables are normally distributed, as discriminant analysis does.

SVM

In classification tasks a discriminant machine learning technique aims at finding, based on an independent and identically distributed (iid) training dataset, a discriminant function that can correctly predict labels for newly acquired instances. Unlike generative machine learning approaches, which require computations of conditional probability distributions, a discriminant classification function takes a data point x and assigns it to one of the different classes that are a part of the classification task. Less powerful than generative approaches, which are mostly used when prediction involves outlier detection, discriminant approaches require fewer computational resources and less training data, especially for a multidimensional feature space and when only posterior probabilities are needed. From a geometric perspective, learning a classifier is equivalent to finding the equation for a

multidimensional surface that best separates the different classes in the feature space.

CONCLUSION

This study proposes a robust hybrid classical-quantum model for 24-hour ahead wind speed forecasting. The goal is to exploit the advantages of two promising methods, classical deep LSTM and quantum machine learning. The innovations/findings are summarized as follows. (1) LSTM is combined with a QNN, which leverages quantum mechanical principles, to provide an unparalleled quantum advantage. A QNN includes an embedding layer that maps classical data into a quantum state, which is then processed by a variational layer with trainable parameters, and then a measurement is made to obtain a classical output. (2) The robust design of this proposed hybrid model is achieved by performing Taguchi orthogonal experiments, considering characteristics of various seasonal datasets.

The hyperparameters (such as the number of hidden LSTM layers, number of hidden LSTM cells, dropout rate, kind of embedding, and quantum circuit depth) of the proposed hybrid model are determined systematically without trial-and-error. (3)

The templates that are used to build the proposed QNN can be made more expressive by repeating each one and cascading them, effectively creating a deep QNN. This results from the quantum principles - entanglement, which states that two or more entangled qubits share information, and interference, which denotes a single quantum state interfering or combining with other quantum states of itself. In this investigation, two repetitions (or depth = 2) is found to yield the best results as a result of constructive interference of the probability of obtaining the correct state, and the destructive interference of that of the incorrect state. (4) Experiments reveal that the proposed hybrid model consistently produces more optimal outcomes than its counterpart classical model and other models, such as RF, XGBoost, SVR, NAR, LSTM, and LSTM autoencoder. Specifically, while the performance of classical models may be comparable for some seasons, a notable decrease is observed during summer – the dataset with different statistical characteristics. The results obtained from this robust design, which integrates a classical LSTM with an expressive quantum circuit, demonstrate its great promise for near-term quantum devices.

Conducting the L18 experiments, evaluating the SNR, and performing an

analysis of means, revealed that IQP embedding works best with ‘StronglyEntanglingLayers’ variational circuit. Moreover, the QNN has a depth of two circuit repetitions, making it more expressive through interference. This design is robust and the least sensitive to variations in the four seasonal data sets. The promising results and consistently accurate predictions amidst different seasonal datasets demonstrated by this study lead to a more optimistic outlook on the potential expansion of quantum computing applications in areas such as solar irradiance forecasting and renewable energy hosting capacity optimization involving quantum computing. Specifically, QC and QNN may contribute in the areas of simulation, scheduling and dispatch, and even reliability analyses in the renewable energy industry. This work did not take into account the effects of noise on the performance of the quantum circuit, as a perfect quantum computer was assumed in the numerical simulations. Future research may explore the impacts of qubit decoherence and loss, incorporating error correction and noise models on prediction accuracy. Additionally, various hybrid architectures and more sophisticated quantum ansatzes may also be employed.

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